

Hemiptera, 3 Coleorrhyncha

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FW Peloridiidae

Hackeriella taylori

Xenophysella pegasusensis

Hack riella ?

Howeria kingsmilli

Note gradually reducing ScP

Peloridaoidea: Karabasiidae: *Karabasia* sp.

FW

FW Peloridiidae

Oiophysa fuscata

Hemidocellus fidelis

Hemidoecus leai

Pantinia darwini

CP- is independent from CA.
 ScP runs basally under R & MA.
 MP basally joins R & MA.
 CuP is reduced.
 AA1+2 is greatly elongated.

Xenophyes cascus

FW Peloridiidae: *Pantinia darwini*

CP- independent from CA, usually strong and recurrent.
MP adjacent basally to R & MA.
CuP reduced.
AA 1+2 unusually long.

Peloridae: *Peloridium hammoniorum*

WING BASE
 A: dorsal view
 B: ventral view

Venation derived, but note CP- in FW is basally independent from CA (plesiomorphy). ScP runs basally under R&MA as is typical for hemipteroids. In HW, AP sometimes crosses anal fold, as in many hemipteroids.

FW Progonocimicidae: *Mesoscytina* sp

FW Progonocimicidae: *Eocercopis oralis* (Handlirsch, 1939)

Note CP- running free instead of being fused to CA (plesiomorphy)
 CuP reduced. Note that cross-veins between RP and AP sometimes in
 HW align more posteriorly to support the posterior wing margin
 (see *Aphrophora* sp. here)